

Factor Influencing University Students Purchasing Of Genetically Modified Food (GMF)

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Abstract

GMF is a controversial issue globally, many consumers, especially in developed countries such as Europe and Japan, refuse to purchase or consume GMF, they claimed that GMF unnatural, harmful to human and environment. Meanwhile, government and producers primarily in developing country insists that GM technology crucial since the current of increasing population is not in line with the growths of the production. Therefore, this study would like to identify university students on their awareness, and factors influence them to purchase GMF. 105 students participated in this study and the questionnaire used to collect the data. Meanwhile, descriptive statistics used to answer the research questions. The result indicated that nearly half (41%) respondents unaware about GMF. For those who are aware, mainly has a positive perception toward GMF, as they claimed the price of GMF cheaper. The study also recommended that campaign on awareness of GMF timely needed as a university student are the future generation, the opinion able to boost biotechnology industry in Malaysia.

Keywords: Factors, influence, a university student, purchase, GMF, Malaysia

Introduction

Genetically Modified Food (GMF) issues, becomes controversial national and globally, due to the unnatural process, as it converted through genetic engineering (Plumer, 2015). Generally, the sources from GM plant, however they turn into more debatable as GM animals are likely to be introduced on the market (World Health Organization, 2018). Basically, GE crop developed by removing a gene from one organism or a specific variety of an organism and next transfer it to a different organism or different variety by recombinant DNA method (Jaffe G, 2016).

Those people, who agreed of GMF, argued that GMF crucial due to scarcity, the current situations that the global population increases but the resources such as land remain the same. The result, conventional farming is unable to produce sufficient food for the population. The number of mal nutrient increased (LR) and to make it the matter worse, a natural disaster such as dried, a flood destroys the plant. Hence, the technologies needed to overcome such problems.

GMF is one of the answers; it develops with the believed it is able to give benefit to the consumer such as cheaper in term of price, and more nutritional value. Besides to support the farmer to increase their yield, as GM crop is more durable also improve the appearance of foods (Brown (2017, Burnett, 2015, and Arujanan, 2017).

Those who are against it claimed GMF damages human health such as allergic reaction, or the possibility of migration of genes from GM plants into a human cell. Besides harm for biodiversity and environment as well possibility of manipulated by greedy farmers who are misuse or unappropriated use of GM crop. Finally, they also believe conventional crops may effect on food safety and food security. (Martino, 2014, Heap, I. 2018, Gassmann A. J., Petzold-Maxwell J. L., Clifton E. H., Dunbar M. W., Hoffmann A. M., Ingber D. A., et al. 2014, (Fridell, 2014)

As overall, Tanius, E., & Seng, S. W. (2015) said, mainly consumers' attitude, perception, and acceptance towards the GM foods were negative. Thus, this study would like to answer the following questions; does the university student aware about GMF? If No, what are the main reasons? If yes what are the factors influence their purchase intention on GMF?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Purchase Intention

Purchase intention is the willingness and likeliness to buy or not to buy something. Literature shows consumers have mix perception on purchasing GMF. For example in China, shows that only 35% of the

respondents will or most likely to purchase and has purchase intention towards GMF. However, a study by Lan Lü, Haidan Chen (2016), in Beijing has contradictory, 73% to 83% of respondents said they purchased GMF.

Education is one other factor contribute to purchase intention, Schnettler, Berta, Miranda, Horacio, Sepúlveda, José, & Denegri, Marianela. (2012), found the consumers who are less educated will buy GMF. Besides, religious and lack of knowledge as a factor of rejection of GMF (Fridell, Amin L, Azad MAK, Gausmian MH, Zulkifli F.,2014). Finally, medical condition, quality of the product, brand reputation and pricing do influence the purchase intentions of GMF (Steven Ho Chiang Yeow, Susan Tee Suan Chin, Jian Ai Yeow and Khong Sin Tan (2013).

Knowledge

Knowledge refers to awareness of or familiarity with various objects, events, ideas, or ways of doing things (Henriques, 2013). Hence, knowledge on GMF of farmers and consumers are essential to promote GMF. Zakaria, Adam, & Abujaja (2014) studied on 305 leaders of Farmer Based Organization (FBOs) revealed that Majority of Leaders of FBOs are aware of GM crops (64%). Another 167 said they have a basic knowledge of GM crops. Majority farmers who have knowledge of GMF had positive viewed. They alleged that GM crops result of breeding high yielding, disease and pest resistance, of crops, plus the capability of solving crop production problems. The remaining 60 classified GM crops as negative, complained GM crops were artificial, it created by scientists who are different from natural crops they knew.

Meanwhile, the consumer also has contrasted opinion, Berning & Campbell, 2017 study on 1200 consumers, found respondents have moderate knowledge on GMF. However, they viewed the federal government more knowledgeable and scientist the most knowledgeable. Aleksejeva I (2014) studied of Latvian Consumer's knowledge on GMF said ordinary tomato does not contain genes, but GM tomato does'. Only 31.8 % knows that 'by eating genetically modified food genes cannot get into the human generative cells and be passed to future generations. However, college students tend to accepted conceptions of GMFs (Heddy, Danielson, Sinatra, & Graham, 2016). Finally, Folkerth, Connor (2015), found almost all or 97% of 335 respondents have heard of Genetically Modified Organisms.

Benefit

Generally, GMF has many benefits towards consumers, farmers or to the environment, as Brown (2017) said that GMF benefit to farmer and producer as the ability to vary of production. GM sugarcane able to produce oil from its leaves and stems for biodiesel production, and it also can produce more sugar that for producing ethanol. Additionally, U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) reported that the genetically engineered salmon, able to reduce the commercial maturity in half the time of wild salmon and using 25% less feed. Plus, it safes to eat as any other Atlantic salmon, nutritious, less impact of the disease, and reducing peoples' impact on the environment (Burnett, 2015).

In Malaysia, Biotechnology Information Centre alleged, the GM crops are very safe due to vetted using extremely stringent research protocols. So far more than 2,000 studies have confirmed that GM food does not pose any health risks and at least 250 scientific organizations around the world endorse GM food as safe (Arujanan, 2017).

Problem

However, some studies also found the negative of GM; the GM crops are killing bees and butterflies, cross-pollination contaminates conventional crops, creates superbugs and superweeds, besides harm the biodiversity (Martino, 2014). The negative impact of current GM crop that leads to loss of trust of farmers, in the case of corn, Heap, I. (2018) reported that some of the farmer's overuse and misuse of glyphosate-tolerant crops in order to destroy weeds result in the development of tolerant weeds. It is similar to the case of using inappropriate use of some Bt corn varieties for rootworm pests, again the development of resistant corn rootworm populations (Gassmann A. J., Petzold-Maxwell J. L., Clifton E. H., Dunbar M. W., Hoffmann A. M., Ingber D. A., et al. 2014). The impact of both cases not only increases of cost to spray additional herbicides but consumer and environmentalist against of GMF. Hence, integrated weed and pest management practices need to use by today's farmers Jaffe, G. (2016).

Another problem of the refusal of GMF was the threat to the human well-being and atmosphere in the long run (Fridell, 2014) and finally, Hassan, S. H., John Kua, S. B. and Harun, H (2016) benefit-risk and perception consumer on GMF depend on their knowledge and GM food characteristics. In conclusion, the consumer is still unsure on GMF (Hassan, S. H., John Kua, S. B. and Harun, H 2016).

Perception

The perception towards GMF will encourage government regulations, consumer acceptance and also the farmers (T. E.Mnaranara1, 2017). Again the consumer's perception on GMF differed, 50% respondents in Europe claimed GMF is harmful (J. Zhang and G. Wang, 2014, Lynn J. Frewer, David Coles, Louis-Marie Houdebine, Gijis A. Kleter, 2014). The perception can increase with their knowledge of GMF and GM technologies (Bredahl, 2013). Therefore, (Besley, 2016) suggested that communication variables such as media exposure, attention and the content itself should use to provide knowledge and directly rise their perception of GMF.

Attitude

Ruth T, Joy N. Rumble, Keegan D. Gay, and Mary T. Rodriguez (2016), indicated that students' attitudes toward GM food influenced by risk perception, knowledge and source credibility. Meanwhile, D. Marques, Christine R. Critchley & Jarrod Walshe (2014), claimed that, the consumer attitude toward GMF associated with higher trust in scientists and regulators but lower trust in watchdog (environmental movement). Consumer more positive attitudes to GM plants rather than GM animals (Marques M. D., Critchley, C. R., & Walshe, J. 2014).

In Bangladesh age and education give a significant effect on their attitude towards the GM product (Abdullah, Afrad, Abdul Hannan Bhuiyan, Haque, & Tofazzal, 2018). They claimed that 81% of respondents perceived biotechnological product in positive favourable (71%) to highly favourable attitude (10%).

METHODOLOGY

The study would like to identify the factors contributes to purchasing intention of GM Food where the target group is a university student in Selangor, Malaysia. 200 students participated in this study, but the return was 105. The questionnaire used to collect the data and the first part, the respondents asked about their awareness of GMF. The second part is to identify, the respondent's opinion on factors contribute to their decision to purchase intention on GMF. Finally, the respondents ask on their purchase intention of GMF. The data analysed by using SPSS and descriptive statistics, correlation, T-Test, and ANOVA used to answer the research question.

FINDINGS

Background of Respondents

Majority of respondents female (66.7%) and 33.3% are male, with age between by age 21 to 25 years old. In term of race, 72.4 % are Malay and single (94.3%). Out of 105 respondents, 59% said they aware about GMF. Meanwhile, 41% said no.

Reason for Not Aware of GMF

As shown in table 1, The five main reasons for respondents do not seem aware of GMF; the highest mean is unfamiliar to GM product (M=4.30; SD=0.708). Next is lack of information (M=4.28; SD = 0.734), followed by SME conquer of GMF market (M=4.23; SD=.782). The respondents said they unaware of GMF due to their support on organic products (M=4.19; SD=.890), finally due to absent GMF product labelling (M=4.16; SD=.843).

Table 1: Five main Reasons for Unaware of GMF (N=105)

No.	Item	Mean	Std. Deviation	Rank
1	Unfamiliar products	4.30	.708	1
2	lack of information	4.28	.734	2
3	SME conquer the market	4.23	.782	3
4	support more organic products	4.19	.890	4
5	lack of product labelling	4.16	.843	5

Purchase Intention on GMF

The next discussion bases on 62 of respondents who said yes that they are aware of GMF. The table 2 shows that the main five factors contribute to the purchase intention towards GM Foods, the majority said, is it is cheaper ($M= 3.66$, $SD= 0.723$); and easy to get ($M=3.66$, $SD= 0.848$). Respondents claimed that they buy GMF due to support of the food industry ($M= 3.52$, $SD= 0.620$), besides influenced by others they know ($M= 3.45$, $SD= 0.717$). The fifth reasons are due to believing that the quality and taste of GMF are better.

Table 2: Five main Reasons to Purchase GMF

No.	Item	Mean	Std. Deviation	Rank
1	it is cheaper	3.66	.723	1
2	it easy to get	3.66	.848	2
3	to support the development of the food industry	3.52	.620	3
4	many people that I know prefer to consume GM food	3.45	.717	4
5	the quality and taste of GMF are better	3.35	.791	5

Factors Contribute to Purchase Intention of GMF

There are many factors contribute to purchase GMF. However, this study focuses only five areas; they are; knowledge, attitude, benefits, perception, and problem.

Knowledge of GMF

In term of knowledge on GMF, the five their main knowledge on GMF were, know that the following are the GMF; soybean ($M= 1.52$, $SD = 0.504$); tomatoes and milk contain ($M= 1.50$, $SD = 0.504$). It followed by potatoes ($M= 1.48$, $SD = 0.504$), and fifth is rice ($M= 1.44$ $SD = 0.504$).

Table 3: Five main of knowledge of GMF (N=62)

No.	Item	Mean	Std. Deviation	Rank
1	soybean contain GM components	1.52	.504	1
2	milk contain GM components	1.50	.504	2
3	Tomatoes contain GM components	1.50	.504	2
4	Potatoes contain GM components	1.48	.504	4
5	rice contain GM components	1.44	.500	5

The Benefit of GMF

There are nine questions asked to respondents, the top five benefits according to respondents stated in table 4. The highest mean score is GMF long-lasting ($M = 4.03$, $SD= 0.701$), followed by GMF able to help the farmer to produce more and quality with a short time ($M = 3.92$, $SD= 0.731$). The third is the price of food decrease ($M = 3.82$, $SD= 0.800$). The forth is GMF able to increase food supplies for population ($M = 3.82$, $SD= 0.800$). Finally respondents agreed that GMF can stand extremes weather ($M = 3.63$, $SD= 0.730$).

Table 4: Benefit of GMF (N=62)

No.	Item	Mean	Std. Deviation	Rank
1	It is long lasting	4.03	.701	1
2	helps farmers	3.92	.731	2
3	decreased food price	3.82	.800	2
4	increase food supplies for the population	3.77	.818	4
5	withstand weather extremes	3.63	.730	5

Problem of GMF

The next, respondents ask their opinion, the problem on GMF to make them refuse to purchase GMF. Table 5, specified the key five problems of GMF accused by respondents. They suspected that the GMF makes people allergic ($M= 3.73$; $SD = 0.793$), and the taste is not natural ($M= 3.68$; $SD = 0.845$). Respondents also indicated that GMF contains toxic ($M=3.65$; $SD=.889$) and able to create new virus ($M=3.63$ $SD=.854$). Finally, they also support the statement GMF can create a mutation in human genes ($M=3.58$; $SD= .821$).

Table 5: Problem of GMF (N=62)

No.	Item	Mean	Std. Deviation	Rank
1	make people allergic	3.73	.793	1
2	unnatural tastes	3.68	.845	2
3	contains toxic	3.65	.889	3
4	create new virus	3.63	.854	4
5	creating mutation in human genes	3.58	.821	5

Attitude toward Purchase Intention of GMF

Finally, the respondents asked their attitude on purchasing GMF, mainly they alleged that they did not buy GMF cause it contained artificial preservatives (M=3.66; SD=.848), however as overall they support GMF by said that GMF was able to support the production (M=3.61; SD=.817) and also handy (M=3.48; SD=.805). they concluded, by claimed GMF worth to buy (M=3.45; SD=.761), and it was a wise to buy (M=3.42; SD=.860).

Table 6: Attitude toward Purchase Intention of GMF (N=62)

No.	Item	Mean	Std. Deviation	Rank
1	contain artificial preservatives	3.66	.848	1
2	support the production	3.61	.817	2
3	very useful	3.48	.805	3
4	worth to buy	3.45	.761	4
5	wise to buy	3.42	.860	5

CONCLUSION

The study found that factors contributing to purchase GMF were a lower price, however mainly respondent has medium knowledge of GMF. They defend that GMF was long lasting. However, they also agreed that one the main problem with GMF is the ability make people allergic. Finally respondent has the positive viewer on purchasing GMF, even though they complained that GMF contains artificial preservatives. It can conclude that the university students still not convincing on GMF although they claimed GMF give benefit and cheaper in term of price.

Base on the result of the study, it is suggested to policymaker, producers, as well as scientists to collaborate to support in this industry and communicate it clearly to consumers, besides education, create an awareness campaign, marketing messages. Standardize labeling necessary, and it should include the correct information such as nutrition fact.

However, this study also has some limitations, such the respondents very small; it may not be representative of all university students; nevertheless the study may become pilot for future study that includes diverse, consumers, race as well as more universities. Second, the research focuses only Malaysian context; the future study is suggested to replicate this study in others country especially neighboured countries such as Indonesia, Singapore or Thailand that may have a similar perception on GMF.

Apart from that, the future study should explore GMF Halal, due to the population in Malaysia majority Muslim, and the Muslim population globally increased. Desilver D and Masci D (2017) reported that as 2010, estimated 1.6 billion Muslims population globally and make up a majority in 49 countries. The report added that it estimates by 2050 the Muslims worldwide will grow to 2.76 billion, or 29.7% of the world's population. Furthermore Halal is mandatory in Islam especially in dietary.

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